

Inverse calculation of liquid crystal parameters using scientific machine learning

Chandroth P. Jisha¹, Alessandro Alberucci¹, Stefan Nolte^{1,2}

1. Friedrich Schiller University, Institute of Applied Physics, Albert-Einstein-Str. 15, 07745, Jena, Germany

2. Fraunhofer Institute for Applied Optics and Precision Engineering IOF, Albert-Einstein-Str. 7, 07745, Jena, Germany

Liquid crystals are fundamental in all modern opto-electronic devices. They have the peculiar property of being intermediate between liquids and solids: in fact, the optic axis of the liquid crystal can be changed locally by applying external perturbations and stimuli [1]. An accurate estimate of the electro-optical properties is of primary importance for both for applications as well as fundamental science [2]. For example, slight discrepancies in the elastic constants can predict huge variation in the phase retardation imparted on the optical field, when used as a tunable waveplate. Scientific machine learning (SciML) has recently found application in all areas of science. Here we use SciML [3] to characterize a liquid crystal cell and go beyond the standard techniques which usually have no access to the point by point optic axis orientation inside the cell.

The advantage of using SciML over a traditional deep learning algorithm is that the neural network also learns from the physics involved in the process. In our case, the continuum theory of liquid crystals is included as an additional cost to the neural network. The neural network is trained on the inverse problem of predicting the elastic and dielectric parameters of the material. Our physics-informed neural network consists of a neural network with one input, 8 layers of 32 neurons each, and 2N output where N corresponds to the number of transverse points in the liquid crystal cell. The two outputs are the reorientation of the optic axis and voltage difference inside the cell. The LC parameters to be predicted are included as a parameter for the neural network. The geometry of the cell is as shown in Fig. 1 a. The schematic flowchart of the training is as shown in Fig. 1 b. The total loss function of the neural network consists of both the loss during training as well as the physics loss coming from the coupled partial differential equation. The retrieved values for the elastic constants and permittivity is shown in the table in Fig. 1 c together with the relative error.

Fig. 1 (a) Schematic of the liquid crystal cell. (b) The flowchart of the training process of the physics-informed neural network.

(c) Predictions of the liquid crystal parameters and the relative error.

In conclusion, we developed a novel method to characterize the liquid crystal parameters. The method is based on physics-informed neural network wherein we trained a feed forward neural network together with the partial differential equation governing the liquid crystal reorientation inside a standard planar cell. Our findings applies to all the numerous photonic applications -mainly light modulation- involving liquid crystals.

References

- [1] S.-T. Wu and D.-Y. Kang, *Fundamental of Liquid Crystal Devices* (Wiley, 2006).
- [2]. D. Bankova, N. Brouckaert, N. Podoliak, B. Beddoes, E. White, O. Buchnev, M. Kaczmarek, and G. D'Alessandro, "Characterization of optically thin cells and experimental liquid crystals," *Appl. Opt.* 61, 4663–4669 (2022).
- [3] M. Raissi, P. Perdikaris, and G.E. Karniadakis, "Physics-informed neural networks: A deep learning framework for solving forward and inverse problems involving nonlinear partial differential equations," *J. Comput. Phys.* 378, 686- 707 (2019).